

NANOEMULSION-BASED COSMETIC SPRAYS: FORMULATION STRATEGIES, CHARACTERIZATION, SAFETY AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract :-

Since the greater stability, improved penetration, and light, sprayable texture, nanoemulsion-based cosmetic sprays have become cutting-edge delivery solutions for natural and herbal actives. The formulation elements, preparation methods, characterisation techniques, and safety issues of nanoemulsion-based cosmetic sprays are all thoroughly examined in this review. The selection of oils, surfactants, and preservatives that come from natural and biocompatible sources is emphasised. In this quickly developing field, the paper also examines current regulatory viewpoints, commercial applications, and research shortages. Although issues like scalability, long-term stability, and sustainable formulation techniques still need to be resolved, nanoemulsion sprays show promise for delivering herbal actives with increased efficacy and consumer appeal.

Keywords : Nanoemulsion, Cosmetic spray, Herbal formulation, Surfactant, Preservation, Characterization, Stability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) defines cosmetics as substances applied to the human body or any part of it with the goal of cleansing, beautifying, increasing attractiveness, or altering appearance. In a broader sense, cosmetics are items that improve skin appearance, increase beauty, and facilitate thorough cleaning. These standards include a wide range of cosmetics-related products, each with a unique function in terms of personal hygiene and aesthetics. A wide range of commercial items, such as hair dyes, shampoos, toothpaste, deodorants, skin moisturisers, anti-aging treatments, and facial makeup, are used to improve one's appearance. This area reflects the range of cosmetics, including items that cater to different aspects of personal grooming and aesthetic tastes.[1] Cosmetics are preparations that have been used by humans for a very long period, mostly for regeneration purposes, and are treasured by both sexes. They can be defined as preparations created from a single ingredient or a combination of compounds acquired from natural or artificial sources, and they are typically applied externally. Cosmetics are "intended to be applied to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance without affecting the body's structure or functions," according to the US Food and Drug Administration (USFDA). This wide definition encompasses any material recommended for use as a component of a cosmetic item, even though soap is expressly excluded from this class. However, this statute does not define "cosmeceutical." The term "cosmeceutical" does not exist, according to the Federal Food Drug and Cosmetic Act (FD&CAAct).

This phrase is only used in the business to refer to cosmetics with therapeutic properties.

Cosmetics are defined as "any substance or preparation intended to be placed in contact with the various external parts of the human body (epidermis, hairsystem, ails, lips, and external genital Organs) or with the teeth and the mucous membranes of the oral cavity with a view exclusively or mainly of cleaning them, perfuming them, changing their appearance and/or correcting body odours and/or protecting them or keeping them in good condition" according to the EUCD. Cosmetics are referred to as "any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on, or introduced into, or otherwise applied to the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance, and includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetic" according to the Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 and the Rules 1945.

Despite these definitions, in a number of nations, cosmetics have a more expansive legal meaning. In many Western nations, cosmetics—such as lipstick, mascara, eyeliners, highlighters, and a few more goods of this kind—are generally seen as purely beautifying things.[2] A lyophobic colloidal system consisting of two immiscible liquids is called an emulsion. The second liquid, which assumes the shape of spherical globules, has the first liquid evenly distributed throughout it. Tiny droplets with widths ranging from 0.01 to 100 μm make up the liquid that envelops the continuous phase. Based on stability and droplet size, emulsions are categorised as nanoemulsions, microemulsions, macroemulsions, or coarse emulsions. Nanoemulsions are heterogeneous colloidal particle systems composed of at least two immiscible liquids. They are also known as submicron emulsions, ultrafine emulsions, and mini-emulsions. One of these liquids is scattered into another

as microscopic droplets between 20 and 500 nm, with transparent droplets between 50 and 200 nm and milky droplets up to 500 nm.[3] Based on the relative composition and dispersal of the more prevalent continuous phase and the internally scattered phases, nanoemulsions were categorised as biphasic (O/W or W/O) or multiple nanoemulsions.

The phases that comprise a nanoemulsion are droplet quantity and overall durability; the phase that is present in a larger volume usually evolves the exterior phase; to determine the type of nanoemulsion that is generated under the specified parameters, the interaction of the many components that make up the nanoemulsion must be approximated. O/W emulsification is recommended when the emulsifier is hydrophilic or, on the other hand, lipophilic. Compared to the hydrocarbon zone, the polar part of an emulsifier often acts as a more effective coalescence barrier.[4] Nanotechnology has the potential to be the biggest engineering breakthrough since the industrial age. Nanotechnology is the term for science and technology conducted at the nanoscale. Thus far, nanotechnology has been used to create a variety of formulations, including nanoparticles, nanocapsules, nanospheres, nanosuspensions, nanocrystals, nanoerythrosomes, and nanoemulsions. Nanotechnology is the process of creating and modifying materials at the nanoscale level to create products. A nanoemulsion drug delivery system is a method for increasing the bioavailability of poorly soluble medications.[5] Because of their ability to improve penetration through the stratum corneum and enable deposition in deeper layers of the skin, microemulsions have been investigated as efficient carriers for spray-based topical delivery. Their superior wetting qualities, small droplet size, and the presence of surfactants and cosurfactants all help to improve skin contact and boost delivery effectiveness.

Microemulsion systems offer extra benefits including focused administration, convenience of use, and improved patient compliance when used with a spray mechanism, particularly for hard-to-reach places like the shoulders, chest, and back. By providing antibacterial qualities, preventing the development of new lesions, reducing inflammation, and cooling the skin, the addition of herbal oils to the oily phase further increases their therapeutic efficacy. Microemulsion-based spray systems, which have demonstrated promising physicochemical qualities and antibacterial activities in topical applications, have been developed and evaluated as a result of these multifunctional attributes.[6] Despite their great efficacy, nanoemulsions have a number of drawbacks, such as kinetic instability, the possibility of Ostwald ripening, and a progressive loss of transparency. Preparing them often requires costly equipment like ultrasonic devices or high-pressure homogenisers. It also notes that many formulators do not fully understand the phase inversion temperature, the principles of droplet formation, and the roles of surfactants, all of which contribute to industries' reluctance to adopt nanoemulsion technology. Despite their obvious advantages, these challenges have prevented their widespread use in cosmetics.[7] Due to its improved safety profile, biocompatibility, and consumer preference for natural skincare products, herbal nanoemulsions have recently drawn a lot of interest

in topical and cosmetic formulations. Recent research has shown that nanoemulsion technologies provide effective loading and distribution of herbal actives, improving skin penetration and therapeutic efficiency while lowering irritation. They are perfect for making lightweight, quickly absorbing cosmetic mists that meet the growing need for non-greasy, natural formulas because of their small droplet size and large surface area. This growing interest in herbal nanoemulsions is indicative of a broader trend in the cosmetics industry toward environmentally friendly and sustainable technology intended to improve product performance and consumer appeal.[8]

II. FUNDAMENTALS OF NANOEMULSIONS:

With droplet sizes typically ranging from 20 to 200 nm, nanoemulsions are colloidal dispersions consisting of oil and water phases stabilised by surfactants. These nanoscale droplets offer the system clarity or a slight translucency and greatly improve the solubilisation of compounds that are poorly soluble in water. Because of their small droplet size, nanoemulsions display remarkable kinetic stability compared to regular emulsions despite being thermodynamically unstable. They are especially well-suited for cosmetic applications, where a light texture, rapid spreadability, and efficient delivery are crucial due to their structural characteristics and physicochemical behaviour.[9] Oil-in-water (O/W), water-in-oil (W/O), and more complex multiple nanoemulsions like water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) are the categories into which nanoemulsions are divided according to the arrangement of their internal and external phases. Because of their lightweight, non-greasy feel and ability to efficiently incorporate lipophilic actives into the distributed nanodroplets, O/W nanoemulsions are the most common in cosmetic formulations. On the other hand, W/O nanoemulsions are useful when better occlusion or water resistance is needed, even though they are less commonly utilised in cosmetic sprays. Multiple nanoemulsions serve some purposes, such controlled release, but because of their multi-phase composition, they require careful surfactant selection and advanced stabilisation procedures.[10] Oil, emulsifying agents, and aqueous phases are the main components of nanoemulsion. Castor oil, corn oil, coconut oil, evening primrose oil, linseed oil, mineral oil, olive oil and peanut oil are just a few examples of the different kinds of oils. An oil and water mixture may result in a simple, transient emulsion that, when left to stand, will split into two distinct phases as the scattered globules come together. Such solutions can be stabilised by emulgents or emulsifying agents. Emulgents are often classified as hydrophilic colloids like acacia, finely split solids like bentonite, and surfactants like spans and tweens. In addition to its emulsifying properties, an emulgent should be non-toxic and compatible with the product in terms of taste, aroma, and chemical stability.[11] The techniques used to create nanoemulsion drug delivery systems are diverse and

show a great deal of overlap. Based on energy needs, the type of phase inversion, and self-emulsification, we have classified the different methods for creating nanoemulsion drug delivery systems.

- High energy methods:
 - i) High-pressure homogenization
 - ii) Micro fluidization
 - iii) Ultrasonication
- Low energy methods:
 - i. Phase inversion emulsification method
 - ii. Transitional phase inversion (TPI)
 - iii. Phase inversion temperature (PIT)
 - iv. Phase inversion composition (PIC)
 - v. Catastrophic phase inversion (CPI)
 - vi. Emulsion inversion point (EIP)
 - vii. The self-nano emulsification method [12]

The long-term durability of nanoemulsions depends on minimising flocculation and coalescence, both of which occur when the interfacial layer around droplets is too thin to prevent merging or aggregation. A stable system requires a strong, flexible interfacial layer that enhances droplet protection and reduces the likelihood of destabilisation. This layer is produced by the right mix of surfactants and co-surfactors.

Optimising formulation parameters, particularly droplet size, interfacial strength, and surfactant packing, increases kinetic stability and prevents the nanoemulsion from degrading structurally over time.[13] Droplet size is one of the key factors affecting the stability and functional efficacy of nanoemulsions. Smaller droplets provide greater kinetic stability by reducing creaming or sedimentation and increasing the interfacial surface area accessible for active delivery. Since these variables have a major impact on the final droplet size, optimising the emulsification method, surfactant selection, and processing parameters is essential for creating reliable and long-lasting nanoemulsion systems. These components have been found to be important factors in maintaining Structural integrity and improving formulation efficacy. [14, 15]

III. TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES FOR SPRAYABLE NANOEMULSIONS

Sprayable nanoemulsions in cosmetics strive for droplet sizes of 20–200 nm to offer low viscosity, optical transparency, and fine atomisation for consistent mist application on skin. These systems are crucial for herbal extract-containing face mists because they maintain spray pump compatibility while enhancing active ingredient penetration. There are two ways to prepare: high-energy methods that rely on mechanical disruption and low-energy methods that exploit thermodynamic instability.[16] High-energy methods are widely used to produce sprayable nanoemulsions because they offer the consistently small droplet sizes required for effective atomisation. One method that creates incredibly stable and spray-ready formulations is high-pressure homogenisation, which uses powerful shear and cavitation pressures to break down coarse emulsions into nanoscale droplets. Ultrasonication is especially useful for temperature-sensitive herbal actives because acoustic cavitation rapidly creates tiny droplets with minimal heat emission. Microfluidization further enhances droplet homogeneity and creates nanoemulsions that are more stable and consistent when sprayed by rapidly pushing the emulsion via microchannels. These high-energy techniques work well together to deliver consistent particle-size control and performance suitable for cosmetic spray applications. [17, 18, 19] Low-energy techniques rely on the intrinsic properties of surfactants and formulation ingredients to generate nanosized droplets without the use of powerful mechanical force. Techniques such as spontaneous emulsification, phase inversion composition (PIC), and self-nanoemulsifying systems (SNES/SNEDDS) produce nanoemulsions through controlled changes in formulation composition, diffusion, or interfacial tension. Because these techniques operate at room temperature and are ideal for formulations including heat-sensitive herbal extracts, they are highly advantageous for sprayable systems. Low-energy methods are also scalable, affordable, and capable of producing reliable, tiny droplets suitable for cosmetic spray applications when surfactant ratios and composition gradients are accurately tuned. [20.21] The development of sprayable nanoemulsions is greatly aided by nano-spray drying, an advanced atomisation technique that uses a vibrating mesh or nozzle system to create incredibly small droplets. Using a carefully crafted nozzle that controls droplet size based on mesh diameter, vibration frequency, and feed properties, this device atomises the feed solution into uniform micro- or nanosized droplets. This method is suitable for formulations that contain delicate herbal components because it ensures repeatability, a limited size distribution, and low thermal degradation of heat-sensitive actives during the drying step. As an example of how nozzle design and spray parameters have a major impact on droplet formation and overall spray performance, the efficient atomisation process also improves encapsulation efficiency, deposition, and stability of the final dried particles. Nano-spray drying serves as a crucial model for understanding the atomisation behaviour required in sprayable nanoemulsion systems because of its delicate operation and exact control over droplet size.[22]

IV. NANOEMULSION SPRAYS IN TOPICAL AND COSMETIC APPLICATIONS

Because of its ability to promote skin penetration and lipophilic active ingredient delivery, nanoemulsions have garnered a lot of attention in topical and cosmetic formulations. Their small droplet size gives them a large surface area, which improves skin contact and promotes deeper diffusion of useful substances. When compared to conventional emulsions, these systems provide advantages such improved solubilisation, higher bioavailability, and superior physical stability, making them suitable for the addition of delicate cosmetic actives. Additionally, nanoemulsions improve visual attributes that are desired in modern cosmetic products, such as clarity, smooth application, and a lightweight feeling after usage. When taken as a whole, these characteristics highlight how well nanoemulsions work as topical cosmetic delivery vehicles and encourage their conversion into sprayable forms for more consistent skin application and consumer convenience. [23, 24] Because nanoemulsion sprays can improve visual skin features and increase skin absorption, they have shown significant promise in therapeutic and cosmetic applications. Over the course of 12 weeks, the Vitamin E nanoemulsion spray described in the study created a consistent, stable composition with particle sizes ranging from 186 to 339 nm while maintaining suitable skin-friendly pH levels between 6.7 and 7.16. Because of its smaller droplet size and more efficient distribution throughout the skin's surface, the nanoemulsion demonstrated better dermal penetration than cream formulations. Particularly with the 5% Vitamin E spray, in vivo evaluations showed significant improvements in moisture content, skin homogeneity, pore size, and a reduction in dark spots, indicating improved anti-aging qualities.

In conclusion, the findings support nanoemulsion sprays as effective, aesthetically pleasing systems that offer better functionality than conventional topical creams.[25] Because of its incredibly small droplet size, which increases skin absorption, improves hydration, and reduces water loss while producing elegant, stable formulations that do not cream or flocculate, nanoemulsions are widely used in the cosmetics industry. They allow for the quick penetration of active substances, need less surfactant than microemulsions, and allow for the production of fluid textures, clear gels, and light lotions. Despite these benefits, nanoemulsions are only kinetically stable and, due to their small droplet size, may be vulnerable to instability mechanisms such as Ostwald ripening and coalescence. Because of their metastable properties, it can be challenging to create microemulsions that allow for lightweight long-term stability, and the formulation needs to be carefully optimised to prevent breakdown.[26] Although microemulsion-based sprays, such as the isotretinoin formulation developed in this study, have demonstrated the ability to convert colloidal systems into strong topical sprays, comparable studies concentrating on nanoemulsions are still lacking. While most

nanoemulsion research still concentrates on conventional forms like gels, creams, or simple liquid applications, this work highlights important aspects of spray formulation, such as optimised composition, better drug absorption, and improved topical administration. Droplet size, stability, and skin penetration are typically given top priority in these investigations, but the other factors necessary for efficient spray administration are rarely taken into account. There are very few publications that address nanoemulsion sprays for dermatological or cosmetic applications, and even those that do focus mainly on formulation and preliminary characterisation without examining atomisation behaviour, spray pattern, deposition uniformity, or spray performance parameters. This highlights a major gap in the literature because nanoemulsions are great candidates for sprayable systems due to their advantageous properties, such as extremely small droplet size and rapid dermal penetration; however, comprehensive studies of nanoemulsion-based sprays are still relatively uncommon.[27]

V. PHYSICOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF NANOEMULSION SPRAYS

During the physicochemical evaluation of nanoemulsion sprays, several important features are assessed to ensure stability, atomisation suitability, and skin compatibility. By measuring droplet size, polydispersity index, and zeta potential, dynamic light scattering is widely used to evaluate electrostatic stability and dispersion uniformity. Basic quality characteristics, such as pH, viscosity, density, surface tension, and refractive index, are evaluated using standard analytical techniques to confirm appropriate sprayability, flow behaviour, and isotropic nature. Morphological investigation using TEM and SEM can help understand droplet form, surface characteristics, and structural integrity. When combined, these evaluations help confirm that the nanoemulsion has the proper physicochemical properties for reliable spraying performance and effective topical administration.[28] Nanoemulsions must be physicochemically characterised in order to assess their stability, homogeneity, and potential for drug delivery. Using devices like the Malvern Zetasizer or Coulter LS-230, which provide information on the mean droplet size and the polydispersity index (PDI), dynamic light scattering (DLS) techniques are frequently used to evaluate droplet size and size distribution. Lower values indicate more homogeneous formulations, and the PDI is a measure of droplet size uniformity. Devices such as ZetaPALS are used to measure the zeta potential, which provides information about the surface charge of the nanoemulsion droplets. Significant electrostatic repulsion between droplets is suggested by high absolute zeta potential levels (usually greater than 30 mV), which improves physical stability. While spectrophotometric or HPLC methods are used to detect the drug content and percentage of drug loading, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is used to investigate the morphology and structure of the droplets, confirming their size and shape. When evaluating the stability, consistency, and efficacy of nanoemulsion

formulations, these factors taken together are crucial. [29, 30] The thermodynamic stability of the nanoemulsion formulations under stress conditions was evaluated using centrifugation (15 minutes at 1500 rpm), heating-cooling tests (six cycles between 8 and 40°C), and freeze-thaw cycles (four cycles between -20°C and 25°C). Formulations that showed no signs of phase separation, creaming, or cracking were selected for further investigation. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was employed to examine the morphology, and a Zetasizer was utilised to measure the droplet size using photon correlation spectroscopy. The drug content was ascertained using reverse-phase HPLC, and the refractive index was assessed using an Abbe refractometer. The physical stability, homogeneity, and appropriateness of the optimised nanoemulsions for further application research were ensured by these tests. [31, 32]

The optimised nanoemulsion's spray performance was evaluated using spray efficiency and spray capacity. Spray efficiency was determined by actuating the formulation onto a filter paper at a predetermined distance of 15 cm and measuring the radius of the wet zone, which indicates the spray's dispersion capability. To find the nanoemulsion's spray capacity, it was sprayed 50 times into a 10 mL measuring cylinder. The total volume dispensed was recorded. The volume per actuation was then calculated by dividing the total volume by the number of actuations. The tests were conducted in duplicate to ensure accuracy and reproducibility. These elements are essential to guarantee that the nanoemulsion spray delivers a consistent and uniform dosage with suitable dispersion qualities.[33] To ensure consistent medication administration per actuation, the optimised nanoemulsion formulation's uniformity of spray content (SCU) was evaluated. Multiple sprays were examined from different containers within a batch as well as at the start and finish of individual containers. Pharmacopeial standards were used to determine the acceptance criteria: for most assessments, the amount of active ingredient per spray should be between 80 and 120% of the labelled claim, with average values for the initial and final sprays falling between 85 and 115%. Additional containers were sampled for supplementary testing to confirm batch consistency in situations where the original criterion were marginally not met. The spray pattern and plume shape were examined in order to assess the pump's and formulation's performance. The spray that is released is influenced by factors like formulation characteristics, metering chamber size, and nozzle design. While the spray pattern was examined from an axial cross-section to determine maximum (Dmax) and minimum (Dmin) diameters as well as to calculate the ovality ratio (Dmax/Dmin), plume geometry was assessed by taking side-view photos of the spray to estimate plume angle, width, and height. To guarantee the consistency of spray characteristics, measurements were taken at two distances from the actuator tip, separated by at least 3 cm, within a range of 3–7 cm.[34]

VI. SAFETY, TOXICOLOGY & REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS:

Safety Consideration:

a) **Hazard Assessment:**

Throughout the supply chain, chemical, physical, and microbiological risks can affect cosmetic items, whether they are manufactured or natural. Heavy metals, insecticides, and persistent organic pollutants are examples of chemical contaminants that can be present in natural components. These contaminants might be introduced by raw materials or processing machinery. Metals like lead and mercury may be added to pigments or UV filters in manufactured cosmetics.[35]

b) **Microbial Contaminants:**

Water-based cosmetics and chemicals with a neutral pH can promote microbial development, endangering both the product's quality and the safety of its users. Although preservatives are commonly used to control microbial growth, their use can be minimised by upholding hygienic manufacturing procedures and lowering the microbial burden in raw materials.[35]

c) **Allergenic Substances:**

Nut oils (almond, peanut, and hazelnut) and certain essential oils (lavender, tea tree, and peppermint) may include allergens. Common botanical allergens, such as coumarin, citronella, linalool, eugenol, citral, and D-limonene, are listed in EU Cosmetic Regulation Annex III and are subject to usage limitations and labelling regulations to guarantee consumer awareness.[35]

a. **Safety evaluation of cosmetic ingredients as applied by the SCCS:**

In essence, the safety of cosmetic goods depends on the safety of their constituents.

The fact that many cosmetic goods on the EU market are made from a limited range of substances gives birth to the idea that the safety of a cosmetic product depends on the safety of its constituents. As a result, toxicity evaluations have mostly concentrated on these components, particularly those that are intended to interact with biological entities and hence provide possible hazards to human health. The development of lists classifying chemicals as permitted, prohibited, or restricted is likewise supported by this reasoning. Annexe II List of compounds that are forbidden Annexe III List of prohibited substances Annexe IV: List of Permitted Colours List of Permitted Preservatives, Annex V List of Permitted UV Filters, Annex VI Two pathways are in use when assessing the safety of substances used in cosmetics. The SCCS is in charge of evaluating the safety of the compounds mentioned in the Annex; on the other hand, the industry that sells cosmetics within the EU is in charge of evaluating the safety of all of their constituents.

As a result, all compounds found in cosmetic products fall under the jurisdiction of the "Responsible Person, RP," as defined by Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009, through the designated safety assessor. This means that the substances specified in the Annex are subject to the SCCS.[36]

b. Toxicological Considerations:

A thorough toxicological evaluation is required for the majority of cosmetic chemicals used at concentrations of 1% or higher. However, many of the compounds that are included in cosmetic formulations are only present in very little amounts, such as impurities, leftover solvents, processing byproducts, or small parts of complex plant extracts. It is neither practical nor recommended to conduct thorough toxicological investigations for these low-exposure compounds, particularly animal studies. The cosmetics industry uses the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) approach to address this problem. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration first used this approach in 1967 as a result of Frawley's research, which suggested that the likelihood of systemic toxicity is low below a certain daily human dose.

The chemical structure-based Cramer decision tree, created in 1978 by Cramer, Ford, and Hall, is used in the TTC framework. Munro, Ford, Kennepohl, and Sprenger developed thresholds based on this classification in 1996, and Kroes, Renwick, Cheeseman, and associates improved them in 2005:

Class I: 1800 µg/person/day Class II: 540 µg/person/day

Class III: 90 µg/person/day (revised to 180 µg/day when excluding organophosphates)

In 2007, Kroes, Renwick, and their colleagues proposed conservative skin absorption defaults based on molecular weight and log P values, further modifying TTC principles for dermal cosmetic exposure. This makes it possible to estimate systemic exposure without requiring a lot of testing. The TTC idea has also shown promise for complicated plant materials. In order to apply TTC to calendula extract, Re, Bianchi, Ruggieri, and Ferraris (2009) excluded components with negligible exposure, such as components present below 0.5%, high-molecular-weight carbohydrates, resins, fatty acid esters, and inert plant elements. The estimated systemic exposures for all other components were found to be within their respective TTC criteria after only relevant constituents were assessed. Because of this, the extract was approved for use in cosmetics at doses of up to 18 g per day. In conclusion, given the chemical structure, concentration, log P, and expected exposure of cosmetic components are known, the TTC approach provides a practical, moral, and scientifically validated framework for evaluating their safety in low concentrations.[37]

Safety Evaluation of Cosmetic Sprays:

The safety evaluation of cosmetic sprays is essential since they release aerosols that can cause inhalation exposure. Particle size, exposure intensity, constituent characteristics, and duration of usage all have a significant impact on the safety of sprays. While respirable droplets smaller than 10 µm can enter the deepest parts of the lungs, aerosols containing droplets bigger than 10 µm usually settle in the upper airways and are readily evacuated. While propellant sprays may yield a tiny fraction of respirable particles, pump sprays typically produce bigger droplets (about 70 µm) and hence present negligible danger of deep-lung exposure. Particle size distribution must be measured for an accurate safety assessment, and this is frequently done using

technologies like laser diffraction, cascade impactors, or time-of-flight approaches. It is crucial to interpret data cautiously since aerosol droplets can change as a result of aggregation or evaporation.

Regulatory agencies recommend using worst-case default values for the amount of spray, airborne fraction, length of exposure, and room volume for evaluating inhalation exposure. More thorough evaluations or model-based methods like ConsExpo may be used if preliminary cautious estimates fail to produce adequate safety margins. The toxicological properties of the chemicals utilised also affect the safety assessment. Inhalation toxicity data are required for propellant gases and volatile solvents like ethanol and isopropanol. Although solid particles, such as polymers, are usually innocuous, very large airborne concentrations of them can cause lung overload. Lipophilic greasy droplets can occasionally cause acute respiratory discomfort. To sum up, systemic exposure, respiratory tract deposition, NOEC/NOAEL values, and margin of safety criteria are all included in safety evaluation. The Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) method can be applied to low-level contaminants. When made with substances that have known inhalation safety profiles and non-respirable droplets, the majority of cosmetic pump sprays are regarded as safe for users.[38]

VII. CHALLENGES AND KNOWLEDGE GAPS

When it comes to safety evaluation, cosmetic spray formulations—especially those that contain natural chemicals or manufactured nanomaterials—face a number of unresolved issues. The substantial variation in the composition of natural ingredients, which may show varying concentrations of active chemicals, allergenic substances, or trace pollutants such heavy metals and microbiological impurities, is one of the main causes for concern. Establishing trustworthy toxicological profiles and standardised safety testing procedures for formulations based on natural components is made more difficult by this discrepancy. Uncertainty about the effects of long-term exposure and the possibility of sensitisation results from the lack of validated, harmonised protocols specifically designed for natural cosmetic ingredients, despite the fact that current regulatory frameworks outline general requirements for safety assessments. [39, 40]

Inhalation exposure from aerosolised cosmetic powders and sprays, particularly those containing ultrafine or nanosized particles, represents another crucial gap. Respirable particle fractions from a variety of cosmetic powders can enter deeper parts of the lungs. The qualities of the device being used, ventilation, application distance, and user behaviour can all have a substantial impact on the exposure levels. Accurate forecasts of inhalation risks are currently hampered by the lack of standardised techniques for aerosol measurement and real-world exposure models. Additionally, there is a dearth of toxicological information for many designed particles used in cosmetic applications, especially with regard to systemic absorption, oxidative stress potential, and chronic inhalation toxicity. [39, 40]

In conclusion, the field lacks thorough inhalation safety studies, uniform aerosol characterisation techniques, and reliable toxicological datasets for both naturally derived and nano-enabled cosmetic ingredients, highlighting the need for improved methodological frameworks and standardised regulatory guidelines [39, 40].

VIII. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Nanotechnology is gradually transforming modern cosmetics by enabling innovations like controlled sunscreen release, enhanced moisturising, anti-aging benefits, and smart delivery techniques. Examples of novel nanomaterials with possible use in lipsticks, mascaras, coloured cosmetics, and treatments for complex skin problems include carbon nanobuds and nanosized metal pigments (beyond TiO₂ and ZnO). Nanoparticles can improve cosmetic outcomes, promote pH- or enzyme-triggered release, and boost skin hydration.

Despite these benefits, the potential risks of nanoparticles necessitate a comprehensive, case-by-case safety assessment.[41]

Nanoemulsions have interesting applications in food, agriculture, healthcare, and cosmetics as delivery methods for bioactive chemicals, pesticides, drugs, vaccines, and alcohol-free scents.

However, they have disadvantages such as poor long-term stability due to Ostwald ripening, potential body accumulation of emulsifiers, and time-consuming, skill-dependent production methods. Despite these drawbacks, their benefits outweigh their drawbacks, and future research should focus on safe, eco-friendly formulation techniques.[42]

IX. CONCLUSION:

Cosmetic sprays based on nanoemulsions, which combine improved skin penetration, enhanced bioavailability, and appealing visual attributes like lightness and sprayability, present a promising avenue for the administration of natural and herbal active ingredients. Safety and efficacy are ensured by physicochemical evaluations, and advancements in formulation strategies, such as high- and low-energy methods, offer precise control over droplet size, stability, and spray performance. Long-term stability and inhalation safety are still problems despite these advantages. Scalability and the variety of natural ingredients. Future research should focus on environmentally friendly formulation procedures, consistent safety evaluations, and innovative delivery mechanisms that ensure both consumer appeal and regulatory compliance in order to fully fulfil the promise of nanoemulsion sprays in modern cosmetics.

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